

O'ZBEK DIALEKTIZMLARI TASNIFI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Hozirgi kunda o'zbek xalq shevalarining bir necha xil tasnifi mavjud. Bu tasniflar turli turkolog va shevashunoslar tomonidan qilingan bo'lib, ayniqsa, I.I.Zarubin, E.D.Polivanov, K.K.Yudaxin A.K.Borovkov, G'ozi Olim Yunusov, U.Tursunov, Sh.Shoabdurahmonov, V.V.Reshetovlarning tasniflari katta ilmiy qiymatga egadir.

Kalit so'zlar: tasnif, xalq shevalari, singarmonizm, metisatsiya, gibridizatsiya.

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Profesor I.I.Zarubin o'zbek shevalarini birinchi marta umumlashtiruvchi guruhlariga birlashtirish, ya'ni tasnif qilishga urindi. U o'zbek shevalarini 4 guruhga bo'lib ko'rsatadi: Xiva, Farona, Toshkent, Samarqand-Buxoro shevalari. I.I.Zarubinning bu tasnifida o'zbek shevalari orasida katta o'rin tutgan, qipchoq (j-lovchi) shevalar va shimoliy o'zbek shevalari hisobga olinmay qolgan.

K.K.Yudaxin o'zbek shevalari tasnifining ikki variantini tavsiya etgan. U o'zining o'zbek shevalari tasnifining 1-variantida o'zbek shevalarining tojik tili bilan munosabati va singarmonizmning saqlash darajasiga qarab, quyidagicha guruhlariga ajratadi:

1. Turk tovush tizimi va singarmonizmni saqlagan shevalar.
2. O'zbek va tojik tillarida so'zlashadigan tojik shevalari (Samarqand-Buxoro va boshqa shaharlarning asosiy aholisi).

E.D.Polivanov tomonidan bir qator o'zbek shevalari va dialektlari o'rganib chiqilgan. E.D.Polivanov o'z tasnifida tildagi ikki holatni ko'zda tutdi:

- 1) metisatsiya (qardosh tillarning chatishuvi);
 - 2) gibridizatsiya (turli tizimdagi tillarning chatishuvi).
- U shevalarda uchraydigan barcha fonetik o'zgarishlarni hisobga olib, o'zbek shevalarini bir necha guruhga bo'ldi. Eronlashish nuqtai nazaridan, ya'ni ba'zi o'zbek

shevalarining tiklanish protsessida tojik tilining ishtirokini hisobga olib shevalarni quyidagicha guruhlashtirdi.

1. Eronlashmagan shevalar.
2. Eronlashgan shevalar.

Y.D.Polivanov eronlashgan shevalarga Toshkent, Qo‘qon, Marg‘ilon, Andijon, Shahrixon tip shevalarini kiritisa, to‘la eronlashgan, ya‘ni tojik vokalizmini o‘zida to‘la aks ettirgan shevalarga Buxoro-Samarqand, Xo‘jand, O‘ratepa shevalarini kiritadi. Eronlashmagan shevalarga o‘zbek-qipchoq (j-lovchi) lahjasi va Farg‘onaning singlarmonizmli qishloq shevalarini (Saroy, Andijon, Yo‘lguzar, Mankent) kiritadi.

Y.D.Polivanov bu ikki xil (eronlashgan va eronlashmagan) shevalar o‘rtasida eronlashishning kuchsizlanishi, gibridizatsiya natijasida turkiylashishi kuchligiga ko‘ra, eronlashgan shevalarni 4 xil tipga ajratadi: 2-tip – Toshkent tip shevalari (Toshkent va uning atrofidagi qishloq shevalari (Xonobod, Telov); 3-tip – Qo‘qon, Marg‘ilon tip shevalari); 4-tip – Andijon-Shahrixon tip shevalari; 4-a tip – uyg‘urlashgan yoki umlautli shevalar (Namangan va unga yaqin qishloq shevalari). Y.D.Polivanov tasnifida yana 2 tip sheva ajratilgan. Bular: 6-tip – Shimoliy o‘zbek shahar shevalari tipi (Turkiston, Chimkent). 7-tip – Shimoliy o‘zbek qishloq shevalari tipi (Mankent, Qoramurut kabi shevalar).

Yuqorida kiritilgan shevalar Y.D.Polivanov tasnifida «Chig‘atoy» lahjasini tashkil qilidi. Y.D.Polivanov tasnifiga ko‘ra, ikkinchi dialekt (lahja) o‘g‘uz dialekti bo‘lib, bu dialekt 2 guruh shevani o‘z ichiga oladi. Bular quyidagilar: 8-tip – Janubiy Xorazim guruh shevalari (Xiva Yangi-Urganch, Shovot, Xazorasp, Yangiariq, Xonqa shevalari) shu guruhga (8-a) Sho‘raxon shevasi ham kiritilgan. 9-tip – Shimoliy o‘zbek-o‘g‘uz guruhi shevalari (Iqon, Qorabuloq shevalari).

Uchinchi dialekt qipchoq lahjasi bo‘lib, bu lahja yetti tip shevani o‘z ichiga oladi. Bular quyidagilar: 10-tip – O‘rta Xorazim shevalari (Gurlan, Bog‘ot, Shobboz shevalari); 11-tip – Shimoliy Xorazm shevalari (Xo‘jayli, Qipchoq, Qo‘ng‘irot, Mang‘it); 12-tip – O lovchi tip (Qozoq-nayman, Farg‘ona-qoraqalpoq shevalari); 13-tip – qurama shevalar (Ohangron vodiysidagi qurama sheva) Uyshun, Ulut qishloq shevalari ; 14-tip – Shimoliy o‘zbek shevalari (Turkistondagi so‘zoq, chalaquron qishloq shevalari); 15-tip – O‘rta-o‘zbek shevalari (qirq shevalari va b.); 16-tip – Janubiy o‘zbek shevalari (laqay shevalari va Afg‘onistondagi qipchoq-o‘zbek shevalari).

Y.D.Polivanov o'z tasnifida o'zbek shvelaridagi taraqqiyotni faqat tashqi omillarga bog'lab tekshirdi. U o'zbek tili va uning shevalarida ro'y bergan o'zgarishlar tilning davrlar mobaynidagi o'z ichki taraqqiyot jarayonining natijasi ekanini anglay olmadi.

G'ozli Olim Yunusov o'zbek shevalarini avvalo uch lahjaga ajratadi:

- 1) o'zbek-qipchoq lahjasi;
- 2) Turk-barlos lahjasi;
- 3) Xiva-Urganch lahjasi.

Bu lahjalar o'z navbatida fonetik va morfologik xususiyatlariga ko'ra ajratiladi.

O'zbek-qipchoq lahjasi 4 shevaga:

a) qirq; b) joloyir-laqay; v) qipchoq; g) gurlan shevalariga ajratiladi:

Turk-barlos lahjasi ham 4 shevaga:

Sayram-Chimkent, Toshkent, Andijon, Namangan shevalariga ajratiladi. Xiva-Urganch lahjasi esa 2 shevaga: Xiva, Qarluq shevalariga ajratiladi.

O'zbek-qipchoq lahjasiga kiruvchi shevalarning fonetik xususiyatlarini quyidagicha ko'rsatib o'tadi:

a) adabiy tildagi y undoshi o'rnida j undoshi keladi: yo'l-jo'l, yigit-jigit kabi;

b) adabiy tildagi g undoshlari o'rnida y tovushi keladi: sigir-siyir kabi.

v) o'zbek adabiy tilidagi g' undoshi v undoshi bilan almashinib qo'llaniladi: sog'-sav, tog'-tav kabi.

Fozi Olim tasnifida qolgan lahjalarning lingvistik farqlarini ko'rsatuvchi belgilar berilmagan.

A.K.Borovkov o'zbek shevalari tasnifining ikki xil variantini tavsiya etadi. U o'z tasnifining birinchi variantiga o'zbek shevalarida uchraydigan fonetik belgilarni (xususiyatlarni) asos qilib oladi. Uning tasnifiga ko'ra o'zbek shevalari ikki guruhga bo'linadi: 1) o-lovchi o'zbek shevalari; 2) a-lovchi o'zbek shevalari.

1. o-lanuvchi o'zbek shevalari. Bu guruhga Toshkent, Samarqand, Buxoro, Kattaqo'rg'on, Farg'ona, Marg'ilon, Qo'qon, Qarshi, Jizzax, Farg'ona shevalari kiradi. Bu shevalarda unlilar soni 6-7 tagacha bo'ladi. Bu shevalarda ohangdoshlik hodisasi yo'qolgan. Bundan tashqari, ularda aksariyat birinchi bo'g'inlarda a o'rnida o qo'llaniladi: ota, bola, soy kabi. Morfologik jihatdan,

jo'nalish kelishigining qo'shimchasi -ga va o'rin-payt kelishigining qo'shimchasi -da bir-biridan farq qilinmasdan ishlatiladi. Bu, ayniqsa, Samarqand-Buxoro shevalariga xos xususiyatdir.

2. a-lanuvchi o'zbek shevalari. Bu guruh shevalarga Samarqand viloyatining qipchoq shevalari, Surxandaryo va Qashqadaryo viloyatlarining qishloq shevalari, Shimoliy Xorazm shevalari kiradi. Bundan tashqari Qozog'istonning janubidagi Sayram, Chimkent, Qorabuloq, Mankent shevalari kiradi. Bu shevalarda unlilar ohangdoshligi saqlangan. Unlilar soni 8 tadan 10 tagacha bo'ladi. A.K.Borovkov ushbu guruhga kiruvchi shevalarni fonetik xususiyatlariga ko'ra yana ikki kichik guruhga bo'ladi:

a) y-lanuvchi o'zbek shevalari;

b) j-lanuvchi o'zbek shevalari.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og’ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

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